

Collaborative Manufacturing Systems: Active Learning from Its Name

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Abstract

Collaboration among partners to form a value network has become necessary as sharing of information at all levels from among physical units on the shop floor to connect with external business processes is so critical for being competitive in a market. Therefore, a course on Collaborative Manufacturing Systems has been recently developed to build students' competence in this aspect. Presented in this paper is how this course has been developed according to the learning experience-focused course design and development process (LEF-CDD). Bloom's Taxonomy, Kolb's experiential learning cycle, and the LOVE learning experience have been utilized for identifying learning outcomes, for planning learning activities for ease of learning, and for the selection of teaching and learning methods for offering a diversified learning experience along their learning journey respectively. Based on the design, the students will actively learn from class discussion, laboratory works, and a term project.

Keywords: Collaborative manufacturing; Bloom's Taxonomy; Kolb's experiential learning cycle; LOVE model; Course Design and Development

1 Introduction

The manufacturing sector continues to have high competition due to product variations and complexity in production. This leads to increase cost of product as a primary driving factor. One solution to drive cost down is to improve efficiency, implement new technology and strengthen company growth. A collaboration between machines, manufacturing systems, or companies is also another way to decrease cost. Interaction with each other seamlessly and instantaneously, in some instances, a collaborative manufacturing systems is needed to adopt. The effective collaborative manufacturing systems would bring a better integration of their product and production processes, planning, and strategies.

Collaborative manufacturing systems can be defined as sharing information between business processes across internal or external partners in the value chain network (McClellan, 2003). In the similar sense, collaborative manufacturing management is defined as "the practice of managing by controlling the key business and manufacturing processes of a manufacturing enterprise in the context of its value networks (ARC Advisory Group, 2001). This capability requires the use, application, integration and synthesis of multiple standards and technologies within and between manufacturing enterprises. The sharing system of information communication, service, production processes, the produce progress of production line, or even the delivery scheduling would achieve to fully ensure the satisfaction of the customers.

The collaborative partners in the value chain networks should be able to share any information even sensitive information such as occasional performance, design of products and expense in manufacturing process. The collaboration also requires the relationship among plant and enterprise applications, markets, value chains, and manufacturing nodes. The objective of collaboration should be consistent and mutually aligned among all partners. In addition, the strategies of collaborative manufacturing are frequently focused on four main areas:

product life cycle management, inventory/production synchronization, distribution order fulfilment and manufacturing enterprise collaboration (McClellan, 2003).

However, the collaboration does not mean to putting every piece of data in a central database. More commonly, a few data sharing requirements were specified, and then make a point-to-point connection for data transformations. Many new systems became candidates for integration, for instance, a manufacturing execution system (MES) as the central integrating point or the Middleware or Enterprise Application Integration (EAI) solutions, which were built on standard messaging systems. When supply chain is included to the focus of manufacturers, the business process needs to include value chain partners to be well suited to business-to-business (B2B) integration (McClellan, 2003). This kind of platform uses plant level production management systems to plan, commit and manage production based on actual demand rather than usual forecast. The advantage of the web could be used for information sharing from variety systems of each enterprise. As a result, collaborative manufacturing systems focus on ways to gain benefits from the Internet and develop technologies to become more competitive.

Collaborative manufacturing system is therefore a connecting between the plant floor to external systems such as internal business processes and external business processes to share information throughout the enterprise. Collaborative manufacturing systems could be strengthening the enterprise to compete as a highly flexible and responsive operation to the flexible demands of customers by using value network partners (Mark Allen Engineering Ltd, 2002).

In general, the process begins with collaboration among value chain members to share information including rules and mechanisms of revenues, costs, marketing, the product and solution design, and business processes. The appropriate plant will receive the order through the value network. Then, the information on the progress of manufacturing process and the quality control will be electronically reported to the related partner. Finally, the product will be delivered with the satisfaction of the customer. It is clear to express that collaborative manufacturing system is not only connecting the Internet to the plant floor, but also including a fundamental change in the strategic value proposition for manufacturers. The collection of systems, processes, and technologies could support and enable manufacturers to have more effectively compete through collaboration with strategic partners (Mark Allen Engineering Ltd, 2002).

The objective of this paper is to create knowledge and develop technical competence for better understanding of future emerging sustainable smart manufacturing systems. The course is creating knowledge and is developing technical competence for better understanding of future emerging sustainable smart manufacturing systems. The course is structured around advanced approaches to manufacturing processes, including manufacturing strategies, high-speed machining, flexible tooling, tool-less assembly, generative numerical control, adaptive and predictive process control, embedded sensors, data and simulation, and nanotechnology.

2 Current Learning and Teaching on Collaborative Manufacturing System

As mentioned above, the knowledge of collaborative manufacturing system becomes important for the 21st century. The collaboration is not only sharing information, but also including well management in the value chain network. To achieve the management of collaboration manufacturing system, four main areas of product lifecycle, inventory/production integration, order distribution, and manufacturing enterprise collaboration are considered (McClellan, 2003). Managing collaboration is not easy to implement to be successful, it requires skills of complex problem solving, critical thinking, people management, etc. to cope with. Therefore, the preparation of knowledge on collaborative manufacturing system for student to be ready for work is necessary. From reviewing literature, rarely existing courses are related to collaborative manufacturing system, and the

knowledge about collaboration is mostly presented in terms of subtopics inside the courses. For example, the knowledge of collaborative product development has been discussed in courses of Cloud Manufacturing (Production Engineering Department, 2014) or Concurrent Engineering and Product Life Cycle Management (Mechanical Engineering Department, 2015). Although some knowledge of collaboration in shop floor level, such as collaborative robot has been existed as a course (Carlisle and Sivadas, 2018), the understanding of value chain network in collaborative manufacturing system is insufficiency. Thus, the course design and development that includes multi-dimensional collaboration in manufacturing system is important.

Beside the knowledge presenting in the existing courses, most of them adopt a conventional teaching and learning approach of knowledge-focused teacher-centered learning that instructors will decide the content what the students should learn; develop teaching and evaluating methods according to the content; and then attempt to make connections between the learning outcomes and teaching and learning methods (Bowen, 2017). As the result of this, students may not achieve to learning outcomes. Student-centered learning has been approved to be an effective approach for engineering education in the 21th century (Mohd-Yusof, 2017). According to this concept, students are imposed in an active role that improve their learning outcomes to be able to apply knowledge for problem solving, rather than remember and understand. Instructors should pay attention to select appropriated teaching and learning methods for students to gain good learning experience. Therefore, this study aims to the course design and development on collaborative manufacturing system, using Learning experience-focused concept. Bloom's Taxonomy theory is applied for identifying learning outcomes, while Kolb's experiential learning theory and LOVE model are employed to design teaching and learning method activities. These will be introduced in the next section before the propose approach for course design and development on collaborative manufacturing system.

3 Learning Experience-Focused Course Design and Development

A study reports that more than half of existing teaching and learning methods provide the same type of learning experience (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap, 2019). A group of researchers in engineering education has then been paying attention to selecting appropriate teaching and learning methods for good learning journeys (Koomsap et al., 2019). They have recently developed a backward course design approach entitled 'Learning Experience-Focused Course Design and Development (LEF-CDD)' which put an emphasis on the utilization of Bloom's Taxonomy (Shabatura, 2018), Kolb's Experiential Learning Cycle (Kolb, 1984) and the LOVE learning experience model (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap, 2017). LEF-CDD aims to obtain a well-designed journey that offers a strong learning experience leading to competence development. Teaching and learning methods are well selected and arranged into the designed journey to foster student experiential learning cycle for every single topic of a course. Along the journey, the majority of students will be engaging with learning activities that assist them in achieving the expected learning outcomes of the course.

With LEF-CDD, a course developer begins by establishing the objective of a course, followed by applying Bloom's Taxonomy to set up the expected learning outcomes that the students, after completion of the course, should be able to perform. At this point, the developer will normally start designing course contents, but with LEF-CDD, the course developer is asked to think about how to assess the students regarding the set course learning outcomes. The course contents are next designed. Learning topics can be seen as touchpoints and are connected to establish a learning journey. A better understanding of the current topic eases the students learning on subsequent topics. Therefore, Kolb's model is applied to create an awareness of the course developer on how each of the topics should be taught such that a cycle can be closed for the topic. The LOVE model is applied along with Kolb's model for the proper selection of the teaching and learning methods to make the learning experience interesting and effective.

4 LEF-CDD for Collaborative Manufacturing System

This section shows the LEF-CDD application for the Collaborative Manufacturing System. The following contents are presented conforming to LEF-CDD process.

4.1 Collaborative Manufacturing System

The Collaborative Manufacturing System course is a 3-credit course consisting of 30 lecture hours and 45 laboratory hours. Students will learn and practice how to apply collaboration in manufacturing system and manage manufacturing collaboration in a teamwork environment. The course development concentrates on student-centered learning. Teaching and learning materials are included with various type, such as slides, videos, case study, games, computer simulation, etc. During lecture session, students are encouraged to participate actively in the discussion. To gain in-depth understanding of the course, some topics such as; plant simulations, collaborative machines, collaborative robots and collaborative material handling system are required to do laboratories. In addition, project based learning are assigned to students to develop and practice several skills; teamwork, decision making, communication, problem-solving, conflict resolution and critical thinking. Presentation are also defined in group projects and individual assignments for personal development and knowledge sharing. In sequence, the application of the LEF-CDD process for Collaborative Manufacturing System will be illustrated by presenting the course objective, the expected course learning outcomes (CLOs), the assessment scheme, the course outline and the planned learning experiences, classified according to the Kolb's and LOVE model.

Course Objective:

Collaboration among partners to form a value network has become necessary as up-to-date information is so critical in a competitive market. Sharing of information among a network of physical units on the shop floor and connecting internal manufacturing processes and business processes with external business processes allow a company to offer a core competence with flexible, responsive operations meeting the expectations of customers and the value network partners. This course aims to build students' competence in collaboration in manufacturing from the board picture of collaborative manufacturing management down to collaboration on a shop floor. The students will learn from concepts, applications, and hands-on experience.

Learning Outcomes:

The students on the completion of this course would be able to:

- CLO1: Recognize a potential collaborative manufacturing in a factory (understand)
- CLO2: Identify a value network for collaborative manufacturing for a business (apply)
- CLO3: Apply collaborative manufacturing management in practice (apply)
- CLO4: Manipulate collaborative robots for collaborative tasks (apply)
- CLO5: Manage manufacturing collaboration on a shop floor (apply)

Assessment scheme:

Course assessment approaches are divided into two methods; formative assessment and summative assessment, as shown in Table 1. It can be seen that class discussion and participation will be the main methods to assess CLO1, while peer assessment in class activities predominantly involve CLO3-5. Presentation and group projects are defined in summative assessment as the activities are more suitable to evaluate at the end of learning.

Table 1. Assessment methods applied to achieve CLOs

Assessment Method/CLOs	CLO1	CLO2	CLO3	CLO4	CLO5
Formative Assessment Method					
Class discussion and participation (5%)	9	9	3	3	3
Peer assessment in class activities (5%)	3	3	9	9	9
Practical exercises (20%)		3	9	9	9
Assignments (10%)		9	9	3	3
Summative Assessment Method					
Presentation (10%)		3	3	9	9
Group project (50%)		3	9	9	9

Note 9: Strong; 3 Moderate; 1: weak

Course Outline:

In this course, three modules are developed based on the learning outcomes. The module's contribution to CLOs is presented in Table 2. In addition, four main laboratories including; laboratories on plant simulation, collaborative machines, collaborative robots and collaborative material handling system are developed to increased students experiences. The topics covered in this course are illustrated in Table 3, and according to learning activities in the course, the sequence of learning stages is determined. Learning experiences based on are also analyzed from teaching and learning method used.

Table 2. Module's contribution to Course Learning Outcomes

Course Module/CLOs	CLO1	CLO2	CLO3	CLO4	CLO5
Module I: Collaborative Manufacturing Management	9	9	3	1	1
Module II: Machines Collaboration on a Shop Floor	3	1	3	9	9
Module III: Man-Machine Collaboration on a Shop Floor	3	1	9	9	9

Note 9: Strong; 3 Moderate; 1: weak

Table 3. Learning Experience Embedded Course Outline-Collaborative Manufacturing System

Module	Subtopic	Sequence of learning stages (Learning experience)			
		AC	AE	CE	RO
I. Collaborative Manufacturing Management	1. Evolution of Manufacturing Systems	1(LO)		12(LE)	13(L)
	2. Collaborative Manufacturing Management Model	2 (LO)	3(E)	12(LE)	13(L)
	3. Collaborative Manufacturing Management Fundamentals and Infrastructure	7(LO)	4(LE)	5(LO)	6(L)
	4. Ontology for Collaborative Manufacturing	10(O)	11(LE)	8(VL)	9(L)
II. Machines Collaboration on a Shop Floor	1. Distributed Manufacturing	17(LO)	18(O)	15(LO)	16(L)
	2. Distributed Arrival Time Control for Real-Time Scheduling	22(LO)	19(LE)	20(LO)	21(L)
	3. Collaborative Material Handling System	23(LO)	24 (LE)	25(LE)	26(L)
	4. Collaborative Manufacturing Processes	27(LO)	28 (LE)	29(LO)	30(L)
III. Man-Machine Collaboration on a Shop Floor	1. Evolution of Man-Machine Collaboration	31(LO)	32 (LE)	39 (LO)	40 (L)
	2. Industrial human augmentation systems	33(LO)	34 (LE)	39 (LO)	40 (L)
	3. Flexible Human-Robot Collaboration	35(LO)	36 (LE)	39 (LO)	40 (L)
	4. Cyber-Human System	37(LO)	38 (LE)	39 (LO)	40 (L)
	Entry stage				
	Fulfil during the group project				

4.2 Discussions

As shown in Table 3, a sequence of learning steps and leaning experience have been introduced into the topics. Based on Kolb's learning cycle (Kolb, 1984), learning has a cycle of four stages; abstract conceptualization (AC), active experiment (AE), concrete experience (CE) and reflective observation (RO). The sequence of learning is defined to be a cyclic order and the teaching and learning methods from LOVE model (i.e. L:Learning, O:Observing, V:Visiting and E:Experimenting) are selected for each learning stage. It can be noticed that AC is the common entry stage for most of the topics because of the modern topics. The abstract conceptualization can navigate student to understand the whole concept of each topic before learning in details. Most of learning cycles are completed in CE and RO stages with group project activities to ensure that students understand and can apply the knowledge for solving problems. The active teaching and learning methods of L and E are frequently seen in the learning experience. These results students have competence to achieve the CLOs. The combination of LEF-CDD, Kolb's learning cycle and LOVE model was employed for Product Design and Development course for teaching master's students at Asian Institute Technology and Thammasat University, Thailand (Koomsap et al., 2019). It was found that students' feedbacks were positive as they were encouraged to express their ideas and improve thinking in different ways. The participant-centered learning in a team environment and learning experiences with respected to Kolb's and LOVE models influence students to complete each learning topic effectively. The teaching and learning of Collaborative Manufacturing System course with the LEF-CDD concept has not conducted yet. Nevertheless, it can believe that students will gain more experiences, knowledge and skills to have their competences for future world.

5 Conclusion

Collaborative manufacturing has become necessary for businesses to compete in a market as it is sharing information across internal or external partners in the value chain network. The preparation of students' competence to be ready for this emerging knowledge is important. Therefore, a course design and development on Collaborative Manufacturing Systems is presented in this paper. The approaches of Bloom's Taxonomy, Kolb's experiential learning cycle, and LOVE learning experience have been applied through LEF-CDD process. The course objective, learning outcomes, assessment scheme and course outline and teaching and learning activities have been conducted. From the designed course, students are put in an active role from the activities of class discussion, laboratory works, and a term project. As the result of this, students will improve their competence to apply the knowledge and skills in other unseen problem.

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